

THE ROLE OF ATTENTION IN PERSONAL PSYCHOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation: This article describes thoughts and theories about the role of attention in the human psyche, the development of activity and the types of attention.

Key words: Attention, involuntary, voluntary and post-voluntary attention.

Attention performs many different tasks in human life and activities. It activates the necessary psychological and physiological processes, and weakens the rest, helps the organization of the information conveyed to the organism in accordance with its actual needs and is selectively carried out with a goal orientation, selective and continuous mental activity in an object or activity. ensures that it is collected in a way. Attention plays an important role in the mental processes of a person, and we will consider the main types of attention in the psychology of a person. These include natural and socially determined, direct and indirect attention, involuntary, voluntary and post-voluntary attention, emotional and intellectual attention.

Attention can be divided into three types according to human activity in the organization of attention: involuntary, voluntary and post-voluntary attention.

Involuntary attention is the concentration of consciousness on an object in accordance with its special nature as a sescendent.

Voluntary attention is a directed, consciously controlled concentration on an object according to the demands of activity.

Attention has its own stages of development. In the first months of a child's life, only the presence of involuntary attention is observed. At first, the child perceives external stimuli that are strong or sharply different.

At the age of three months, the child begins to be more interested in objects that are integrally related to his life. At the age of 5-7 months, the child can observe, hold, and take some object in his mouth for a long enough time. His interest in bright and shiny objects is especially evident. This indicates the full development of involuntary attention

Attention is the focus and concentration of mental activity on something. This is a general definition of animal as well as human attention. Human attention can

be studied as the direction and concentration of a person's attention on certain objects, while being distracted from other objects. It follows from this definition that the important features of attention are its direction and concentration.

Under the direction of mental activity lies its selective feature, that is, the separation of specific objects and events that are important for the subject from the environment. the concept of direction also includes the preservation of mental activity over a certain period of time.[1]

Another characteristic of attention is its concentration, which explains the degree of immersion in the activity. The more complex the task, the stronger the intensity and tension of attention should be, that is, it requires deep penetration into the activity. On the other hand, concentration is related to distraction from other extraneous things. Otherwise, if you can't be distracted by extraneous things, it will be difficult to complete the task.

orientation and concentration are inextricably linked. When you direct your attention to something, you are at the same time concentrating on it. And on the contrary, when you concentrate on something, you direct your mental activity to it. The direction of attention is related to the transition from one activity to another, and concentration is related to deepening in an activity.

To understand the role of attention in human mental activity, imagine yourself looking at a group of objects. Some objects in the center of your field of vision are perceived more clearly, while those on the edge of your field of vision are perceived differently. A similar phenomenon can be made with regard to our consciousness: the essence of our activity occupies the center of our consciousness; and those that are not important are pushed aside from our consciousness. But it can also be the other way around: you are looking at some object and thinking about something else. In this case, the "central area" of your mind is not occupied with what you see, but with what you think.

If we depict our consciousness graphically, it is necessary to draw it in the form of two circles, one on top of the other. The big circle is called vague consciousness, and the small circle is called clear consciousness or attention.[2]

The orientation and selective nature of mental cognitive processes is related to attention. Attention determines the accuracy and consistency of perception, the strength and selectivity of memory, the direction and efficiency of mental activity, in short, the quality and results of cognitive activity in general.

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